

PFAS Data Hub: An open data portal featuring geovisualisation - Complementary Material

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Abstract. This document is an appendix to the article X⁷ providing a detailed quantitative analysis of the data available in the PFAS Data Hub in November 2025.

As of November 2025, the PDH dataset⁸ contains 940,066 data points. Each data point is associated with 21 attributes describing its provenance, its location, the nearby human activities, and the samples collected at this point (if any). At a given location, there may be several data points with samples taken on different dates or in different matrices. These are usually data from institutional measurement programs, like drinking water or surface water quality monitoring. A set of PFAS measurements is always attached to a data point via the nested attribute **pfas_values**. This set is empty for points that are not of the “measurement” category. In total, 20,770,342 individual PFAS concentrations are nested within the 940,066 data points. Each concentration is associated with 6 attributes describing the substance being measured, and the value of its concentration.

In the remainder of this appendix, we detail the nature of the attributes used to describe the data points and the measured concentrations in the dataset. We comment on the most common values, the density of points for some specific values, and the proportion of missing values.

Provenance of a data point

Six of the 21 attributes provide information about the origin of the data associated with a point, namely : **dataset_id**, **dataset_name**, **source_text**, **source_type**, **source_url** and **data_collection_method**.

The **dataset_id** and **dataset_name** attributes are integer and string identifiers for the original datasets from which the points originate. There are 116 unique identifiers, with frequencies of occurrence ranging from 1 to 388,080 (mean is 8213 and median is 207). The most common dataset names and the distribution of the number of points per dataset identifiers are shown in figures 1a and 1b respectively. Most of the dataset identifiers have a low frequency (around 100), and few of them have a high one (above 10,000). There are no missing values for these two attributes.

⁷ The full reference to the article (with DOI) will be inserted once it has been published.

⁸ <https://pdh.cnrs.fr/fr/>

the name of the source, the second to its type between “Authorities”, “Scientific article”, “OSINT” (Open Source INTelligence), “Company”, “Press inquiry”, “Journalism investigation” and “NGO” (Non Governmental Organisation), and the last to a reference to the actual source as an hypertext link. Figure 2 shows the most frequent source names among the 272 unique ones in the dataset. Figure 3a shows the frequency of each source type. Figure 3b presents the number of data points per source type and point category. Most of the data point come from authorities, but "Measurement" data points come from almost every type of source. The main sources are “ADES”, “Naiades” and “Databank Ondergrond Vlaanderen”. Only 0.06% of values are missing for the first attribute, none for the second one and 2.30% for the last one.

Fig. 4: Analysis of the `data_collection_method` attribute

The `data_collection_method` attribute describes the method used to collect the original dataset from its source with a string value among “Public data - API”, “Public data - Download”, “Public data - Scraping”, “Press inquiry”, “FOI”, “OSINT”. As shown in figures 4a and 4b, most of the data points in the dataset come from public data, especially "Measurement" points. There are 3.24% of missing values for this attribute.

Location of a data point

Five of the 21 attributes are relative to the location of data points, namely: **lat**, **lon**, **country**, **city** and **name**.

The **lat** and **lon** attributes correspond to the coordinates of the data points in the World Geodetic System. There are 106,643 unique locations (pairs of coordinates) in the dataset. For each location, there is a minimum of one data point and a maximum of 844 data points (mean is 8.5 and median

is 2). Most of the locations are associated with less than 100 data points. The coordinate attributes have no missing values.

Fig. 5: Most frequent values for the **country** attribute

Fig. 6: Most frequent values for the **city** attribute

Fig. 7: Distribution of unique locations, data points and measures per **country**

The **country** and **city** attributes identify the locations in a more user-friendly form. There are 33 and 34 440 unique country and city names in the dataset. The most frequent ones are shown in figures 5 and 6. The bar chart in figure 7 presents the number of locations and data points per country. Most of the data points in the dataset are located in France (78.6%) and Belgium (5.57%). There are 0.15% of missing values for the first attribute, and 54.47% for the second one. Note that this is expected as some points are not located in a specific city or country (e.g. in the sea).

Fig. 9: Distribution of points per **category**

The **category** attribute defines the type of point by specifying the human activity associated with a location. As shown in figure 9, most of the data points in the dataset are "Measurement" locations. There are no missing values for this attribute.

(a) Distribution of points per **type**

(b) Distribution of points per **type** and **category**

Fig. 10: Analysis of the **type** attribute

(a) Distribution of points per **sector**

(b) Distribution of points per **sector** and **category**

Fig. 11: Analysis of the **sector** attribute

The **type** attribute provides additional information about the human activity referred to in the **category** attribute, and the **sector** attribute about the activity referred to in the **type** attribute if its value is "Industrial site" (some "Measurement" points are concerned, as shown in the heatmap of figure 10b). The existing types of activities are listed in the bar chart and in the pie chart of figures 10a and 11a. The heatmap of figure 11b shows that most of the data points attached to an industrial sector are presumptive data points, except for some manufacturers of plastics in primary forms, refined petroleum products and rubber and plastic products that are known PFAS users,

and some finishing of textiles factories that are associated with measurements. There are no missing values for the **type** attribute and, as expected, 99.37% of values are missing for the **sector**.

Samples attached to a data point

Six attributes provide information about the samples attached to a data point, namely : **matrix**, **unit**, **date**, **year**, **pfas_values**, **pfas_sum**. If the data point is not a "Measurement" location, **pfas_values** is an empty set and all the other attributes have missing values.

Fig. 12: Distribution of unique locations, data points and measures per **matrix**

The **matrix** attribute specifies the environment in which the sample was done. In the dataset, the most frequent matrices are water-related, e.g. “Surface Water” or “Groundwater”. When the matrix is unknown for a given point, the attribute value may be missing or assigned to ‘Unknown’. The number of unique locations, data points and the total number of concentration measures (all dates and all PFAS combined) per matrix can be estimated with the figure 12. There are 1.33% of missing values for the **matrix** attribute. In the figure, these missing values are counted in addition to the values marked as “Unknown” matrix in the dataset.

(a) Distribution of points per **unit**

(b) Distribution of measures per **matrix** and **unit**

Fig. 13: Analysis of the **unit** attribute

The **unit** attribute relates to the concentration measurements sampled. All measures at a specific data point share the same unit. The number of locations, data points and measures per unit are shown in the figure 13a. As liquid matrices are more frequent in the dataset, so is the “ng/l” measure of concentration in liquids. A focus on the distribution of the number of measures per matrix and per unit is presented in the figure 13b. In most cases, multiple units are used for measures in each type of matrix. For practical reasons, a duplicate of this attribute is nested inside the **pfas_values** attribute. The **unit** value is never missing for points whose category is "Measurement".

Fig. 14: Distribution of points per **date**

(a) Distribution of points per **year** and **country** (b) Distribution of points per **year** and **matrix**

Fig. 15: Analysis of the **year** attribute

The **date** and **year** attributes index the data points in time. Dates range between January 1977 and October 2025 and cover 33 unique years. The distribution of dates is plotted in the figure 14. Most of the dates are after 2010 or, to a lesser extent, between 2000 and 2010, with a peak of values in 2022. The two heatmaps in figures 15a and 15b show the distribution of data points per year and per country or matrix. Samples in some matrices like “Suspended matter” correspond to more recent

data points while others like the ones in “Biota” are better distributed over the time period covered in the dataset. Overall, 2.48% and 1.33% of values are missing for the **date** and **year** attributes, respectively. The difference is expected as only the year is known for some data points, not the precise date. For "Measurement" data points specifically, there are 0.64% of missing values for the **date** attribute, and none for the **year** attribute. On the heatmaps, lines with values only equal to 0 (e.g. Ireland, Sewerage) correspond to countries or matrices where all the year attribute values for all the points are missing.

Fig. 16: Distribution of points based on the number of measures attached to the point

The **pfas_values** attribute is an array containing a set of PFAS concentrations measured at a certain location, at a certain time and in a certain matrix. As shown in the figure 16, the number of measures per point varies between 0 and 88. Each measure is described by six attributes: **cas_id**, **substance**, **isomer**, **value**, **less_than** and **unit**.

(a) Most frequent values for the **cas_id** attribute

(b) Most frequent values for the **substance** attribute

(c) Distribution of measures per **cas_id**

(d) Distribution of measures per **isomer**

Fig. 17: Analysis of the **cas_id**, **substance** and **isomer** attributes

The **cas_id**, **substance** and **isomer** attributes nested in **pfas_values** describe the type of PFAS whose concentration is measured. The two word clouds in figures 17a and 17b show the most frequent CAS ID and substance names among the 273 and 287 unique values (respectively) included in the dataset. The first bar chart in figure 17c presents the distribution of the number of measures per CAS ID. As represented, the majority of substances are associated with less than 1000 measures. Nevertheless, the most frequent PFAS are associated with several tens or even hundreds of thousands of measures. The figure 17d shows that most of the values of the isomer attributes are missing (99.6%). Indeed, this attribute is irrelevant for most of the substances: only a few of them can be specified as “branched” or “linear” molecules. There are no missing values for the other two attributes.

(a) Proportion of measures above the LOD/LOQ

(b) Distribution of measures above and below the LOD/LOQ per **date**

Fig. 18: Analysis of the **value** and **less_than** attributes (part 1)

(a) Distribution of measures above and below the LOD/LOQ per **matrix**

(b) Distribution of measures above and below the LOD/LOQ per **substance**

Fig. 19: Analysis of the **value** and **less_than** attributes (part 2)

The **value** and **less_than** attributes nested in **pfas_values** correspond to the concentration measures themselves, respectively if the concentration is above or below the LOD/LOQ. As shown in the figures 18a, 18b, 19a and 19b, the proportion of values above the LOD/LOQ varies according to the matrix, unit, date and type of PFAS considered. Overall, 95.2% of concentration measures in the dataset are below the LOD/LOQ. However, for some common PFAS such as PFOS, this ratio is more balanced around 50/50 above/below (see figure 19b).

(a) Distribution of measures per concentration (for value) (b) Distribution of measures per concentration (for less_than)

(c) Distribution of value for the main substances

Fig. 20: Analysis of the value and less_than attributes (part 3)

The concentrations above LOD/LOQ range between 0.0002 and 509 000 000 ng per l/kg/kg fw/kg dw. The mean value is 15 871, and the median is 9.7. The concentrations below LOD/LOQ

range between 0.001 and 64 000 000. The mean is 252 and the median is 10. As shown in figures 20a and 20b, only a few measures have a very high concentration. These could be outliers. The figure 20c presents the distributions of concentrations for the most frequent PFAS in the dataset. Mean values are represented as dotted lines. They are mostly located outside of the boxes, on the right of the straight lines inside the boxes (representing the median values). This is typical of data series with few very high values.

Fig. 21: Distribution of the **pfas_sum** values per **matrix** and **unit**

The **pfas_sum** attribute, which is not nested within **pfas_values**, sums up all the PFAS concentrations above the LOD/LOQ for a given data point. For data points associated with at least one concentration measure above the LOD/LOQ, values of this attribute range between 0.001 and 800 245 054 ng per l/kg/kg fw/kg dw. The mean is 46 845, and the median is 17.9. The figure 21 plots the distribution of the attribute values per matrix and per unit. It reveals that most of the values for the combinations of matrices and units “Groundwater” in “ng/l”, “Groundwater” in “ng/kg dw” and “Drinking water” in “ng/l” are equal to 0. Some high values increase the mean values for these combinations. For other combinations like “Biota” in “ng/kg fw” or “Leachate” in “ng/l”, most of the values are concentrated around specific values greater than 0. There are no missing values for this attribute.

A last nested attribute called **details** gathers various additional metadata to describe the different data points. The most frequent ones are shown in the figures 22a and 22b. For each data point, there are between 0 and 53 additional metadata provided (mean is 3.2, median is 2).